

ADMINISTRATIVE SUPPORT, PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE, AND STUDENT SATISFACTION IN THE TEACHING OF RONDALLA UNDER THE SPECIAL PROGRAM IN THE ARTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between administrative support, teaching methods, and student satisfaction in Rondalla lessons within the SPA program in Region III. Using a descriptive research method, the researchers gathered data through stratified and purposive sampling. This involved collecting information from 43 music teachers and 217 students at 14 secondary schools. Based on the results, music teachers view high levels of administrative support in relation to different variables such as the determination of the need for musical instruments and provision of feedback. Pedagogical approaches like unscripted instructions are used by music teachers to cater to various cultures of students. Student satisfaction is seen as excellent with respect to instructional, engagement, and learning outcomes where the learning outcome includes students' enhanced ability in note reading and performance skills. Although these favorable outcomes were achieved, the educators reported serious problems in gaining access to specialized professional development courses and reflective teaching. Therefore, the research established that although administrative assistance and students' satisfaction are highly satisfactory, there remains an urgent need to build capacity. The action plan was devised to solve the weaknesses, which involved training that would be specifically designed to cater to music specialization. It is recommended by the researcher that improvements in infrastructure like having special music classrooms be considered, along with implementing the suggested action plan.

Keywords: *Administrative, Pedagogical Practice, Satisfaction, Rondalla*

INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, at the international and national levels, there has been a realization of the significant contribution of arts education, and more so music, to the overall development of students. Recent research proves that music education has a positive impact on students' cognitive, emotional, and social development beyond the confines of mere artistic expression. Sun (2022) discovered that learning music positively impacts students' academic performance and socio-emotional well-being, as evidenced by enhanced self-efficacy and self-esteem. Likewise, Diz-Otero et al. (2023) discovered that music education positively impacts critical soft skills like working together, communicating, and flexibility, which are vital in the overall development of students.

The Special Program in the Arts (SPA) is a specialized curriculum project established by the Department of Education (DepEd) to identify, develop, and support students with exceptional skills in various creative disciplines. These disciplines include Creative Writing, Music, Theatre Arts, Visual Arts, Media Arts, and Dance (Ballet and Folk). The program aims to cultivate "excellent young artists who are holistically developed" while also preserving and promoting Filipino cultural heritage (DepEd, 2016). The program's significant impact on creating a culturally responsive and artistically enriched education system is demonstrated by its dual goal of nurturing the artistic potential of individual students and sustaining the national cultural identity.

Recently, music education has shifted from a pedagogical paradigm based on the transmission of traditional praxis to an approach that is more focused on the overall development and personal growth of pupils. If music is considered a human mode of aesthetic communication that involves creative and emotional dimensions (Williams, 2019), the main educational goals of music education should shift from "learning to play" to "learning to live with music".

The SPA encourages students to specialize in music to develop their instrumental skills and cultural awareness. By emphasizing the relationship between Filipino cultural heritage, music theory, and history, DepEd sought to encourage long-term singing and playing abilities in 2016. This all-encompassing approach supports its goal of developing well-rounded young artists by enhancing students' performance, theoretical knowledge, and contextual awareness. During modular distance learning, DepEd Region III created its own customized SPA Music Modules to replace the finalized Self-Directed Learning Modules from the Central Office (Garcia & Santos, 2021). Regional offices were able to show their leadership and agility in meeting instructional needs by working with the National Commission for Culture and Arts (NCCA). Although local responsiveness is enhanced by these programs, curriculum coherence and regional equity may be hampered, particularly if central funding or instructions are not received at all or are delayed.

Music education has become increasingly acknowledged as a central element of overall child development, adding to artistic competence but also powerfully shaping cognitive, social, and emotional development. Rather than an add-on to the curriculum, it

is a key factor in the formation of students' identities, the encouragement of creativity, enhancement of executive functioning, and the development of emotional resilience (Southgate & Roscigno, 2021; Hallam, 2019). This rich impact places music education at the center of a balanced curriculum that enables lifelong learning and well-being.

While music education is widely accessible—with about 92% of students having access in 2019, there still exists a profound participation gap, since only 49% of students take part in these provisions (NAMM Foundation, 2019). This gap emphasizes the immediate imperative for creative and inclusive pedagogies that not only provide access to music education but also make it enticing and meaningful to students' experiences. Closing this gap is essential to guaranteeing the advantages of music education are equitably realized and maintained among varied learning populations (Sun, 2022; Abril, 2021).

This research provided a close reading of teaching Rondalla in the music specialization classes of the Special Program in the Arts (SPA) in Region III. This was in line with SPA's vision of developing artistic potential through experience-based and student-centered learning systems (Department of Education, 2020). This emphasized the pedagogic benefits of improvisational teaching in developing cognitive flexibility, affective expression, social interaction, and musical imagination (Biasutti, 2020; Abril, 2019).

Further, recurring in the analysis was the key role of robust administrative support, provision of tools, funding, professional growth, and policy coherence, in facilitating teachers to put into practice creative, adaptable teaching (Rinta & Welch, 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023). However, the report further indicated key systemic issues, including inadequate music-specialist teacher training, restricted access to facilities and resources, and structural hindrances due to policy imbalances and irregular funding priorities (Sibanda & Blignaut, 2022; Bautista & Tan, 2021). As a response, the research suggested a well-rounded set of strategic interventions aimed at developing administrative infrastructure, establishing teacher capacity through ongoing professional learning, and developing rich learning environments that promote effective pedagogical practices in teaching Rondalla under SPA music programs.

Moreover, one function of administrators is to address concerns in the school. The application of procedures, equipment, and expertise to resolve conflicts in a polite and innovative manner is known as conflict management. It involves the capacity to settle disputes amicably with powerful communication techniques like aggressive speaking and active listening. Handling disagreement is a skill. It is an art form that you develop, not perfect. Having leaders who live up to their words, coaching, and skill-based training can all help people become more adept at handling conflict. Organizations can improve their ability to handle conflict and train personnel to be conflict-competent by enlisting the direct assistance of conflict resolution professionals. Effective leaders understand the value of these abilities and how they affect the productivity and well-being of their company. They are also aware that deficiency in these abilities can result in low morale, low output, and

low retention rates among employees. The cost of developing conflict competent employees is a fraction of the cost of unresolved conflict (Kemal Kayikçi et. al, 2017).

The purpose of this study was to explore the nature and extent of these music teachers' administrative support, the characteristics and effectiveness of their instructional methods, and the resulting student outcomes in terms of instrumental proficiency and appreciation. Identification of such dynamics was important because past research has established that areas of low resources, a lack of specialized training, and weak administrative support negative impact implementation (Brillantes, 2022; Leocario & Pawilen, 2015). This also aimed to elucidate the experiences of both teachers and students, identify gaps in the current implementation of the SPA music program, and propose recommendations to improve the quality of music education, particularly the specialized music teachers, and by examining these factors.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the various facets of administrative support, Pedagogical practice, and student satisfaction in the teaching of Rondalla under Special Program in the Arts (SPA), with a particular focus on music specialization classes handled by music teachers in Region III.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What is the level of administrators' support in the teaching of music in the SPA program along the following areas:
 - 1.1 musical instruments,
 - 1.2 address concerns,
 - 1.3 giving feedback,
 - 1.4 professional developments, and
 - 1.5 teaching method?
2. What is the extent of pedagogical practices by music teachers in the SPA program?
3. What is the level of student satisfaction for the teachers of music in the SPA program along:
 - 3.1 quality of instruction,
 - 3.2 student engagement, and
 - 3.3 student outcomes?
4. What are the challenges encountered by music teachers?
5. What action plan can be developed to improve the quality of music education?

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative-descriptive design was utilized in this study. The researcher gathered and analyzed numerical data and followed up with a phase that explored and explained those results in more detailed process. This approach was specifically chosen

to provide both wide-ranging insights and a deeper understanding of the context. This method was especially suitable for complicated educational research situations, like evaluating how specialist teachers deliver lessons in specialized arts programs, where it's important to understand both measurable trends and personal experiences.

The quantitative phase employed as a descriptive design. Numerical data were collected to describe the administrative support provided to music major teachers, their teaching strategies and SPA Music program student outcomes.

Structured questionnaires were distributed to a broader sample of students and music teachers in the SPA.

The researcher utilized an online survey as the primary data collection tool, allowing participants to respond at their own pace while ensuring a larger sample size within a shorter period. To begin with, a formal request was submitted to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent to be forwarded to the Regional Office for approval, followed by notifications to school heads and consent requests for participants. Selected participants received the survey questions in advance to reflect on their experiences. The survey was conducted at a convenient time to avoid class disruptions, using online platforms like Messenger, or Google Form ensuring safety and compliance with DepEd's remote data-gathering policies.

The research focused in Region III, on public secondary schools that offer a Special Program in the Arts (SPA) with a specialization in music. The primary focus was on the selected schools in Region III that offers Rondalla, as they have been recognized for their involvement in DepEd programs and for hosting schools with SPA programs.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program
in terms of Musical Instruments

No.	Administrative Support		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	My school administration provides sufficient resources (instruments, materials) for music instruction.	3.70	High Support
2	In case of unavailable music instrument, my school administration finds support from stakeholders.	3.52	High Support
3	My school administration plans project to raise funds for musical instruments.	3.67	High Support
4	My school administration determines the needs of teachers in terms of musical instruments.	3.86	High Support
5	My school administration maintains the quality of musical instruments and do repairs if needed.	3.43	High Support
Overall Mean		3.64	High Support

Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High Support
3.40-4.19	High Support

2.60-3.39 Moderate Support
 1.80-2.59 Slight Support
 1.00-1.79 No Support

Table 1.2
Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program
in terms of Addressing Concerns

No.	Administrative Support		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	My principal/coordinator holds regular meeting to determine and address concerns of music teachers.	3.65	High Support
2	My principal/coordinator actively listens to my concerns regarding music teaching.	3.86	High Support
3	My principal/coordinator conducts a regular monitoring of teachers' performance.	3.79	High Support
4	My principal/coordinator addresses music teachers' concerns on time.	3.63	High Support
5	My principal/coordinator involves music teachers in addressing concerns related to the subject.	3.70	High Support
Overall Mean		3.73	High Support

Mean Verbal Interpretations
 4.20-5.00 Very High Support
 3.40-4.19 High Support
 2.60-3.39 Moderate Support
 1.80-2.59 Slight Support
 1.00-1.79 No Support

Table 1.3
Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program in terms of
Giving Feedback

No.	Administrative Support		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I receive timely feedback on my music teaching practices.	3.79	High Support
2	The feedback given to me by my administrator is constructive in nature.	3.86	High Support
3	The feedback given to me is based on classroom observation.	3.79	High Support
4	My administrator's way of giving feedback is very professional and objective.	3.63	High Support
5	I receive feedback that contribute to my professional growth.	3.70	High Support
Overall Mean		3.75	High Support

Mean Verbal Interpretations
 4.20-5.00 Very High Support
 3.40-4.19 High Support
 2.60-3.39 Moderate Support
 1.80-2.59 Slight Support
 1.00-1.79 No Support

Table 1.4
Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program
in terms of Professional Development

No.	Administrative Support		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	The school administration encourages teachers to participate in seminars and trainings.	3.81	High Support
2	There are adequate professional development opportunities for music teachers at my school.	3.78	High Support
3	The school has programs for teachers in the graduate studies education.	3.72	High Support
4	The school provides access for teachers in different graduate studies universities and colleges.	3.53	High Support
5	The school looks for possible help and assistance for teachers enrolled in the graduate studies.	3.51	High Support
Overall Mean		3.67	High Support

Mean Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00 Very High Support
3.40-4.19 High Support
2.60-3.39 Moderate Support
1.80-2.59 Slight Support
1.00-1.79 No Support

Table 1.5
Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program
in terms of Teaching Method

No.	Administrative Support		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	My administration expose me to different teaching methods and strategies in music.	3.63	High Support
2	My administration provides training and capacity building in handling music subject.	3.80	High Support
3	My administration provides technical assistance to music teachers.	3.79	High Support
4	My administration plans projects that support the teaching-learning process in music.	3.54	High Support
5	My administration supports my efforts to try new or adaptive teaching methods in music	3.70	High Support
Overall Mean		3.69	High Support

Mean Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00 Very High Support
3.40-4.19 High Support
2.60-3.39 Moderate Support
1.80-2.59 Slight Support
1.00-1.79 No Support

Table 2
Music Teachers' Extent of Pedagogical Practices in the SPA Program

No.	Pedagogical Practices		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I frequently use student-chosen music in my lessons.	3.77	Agree
2	I often adapt my lesson plans in real-time based on student responses or needs.	3.95	Agree
3	I incorporate elements of improvisation or spontaneous music-making in my classes.	3.93	Agree
4	I encourage students to learn music by ear rather than solely by notation.	3.93	Agree
5	I integrate technology (e.g., music apps, digital tools) into my music lessons.	3.88	Agree
6	I use music and movement activities to enhance student engagement.	3.91	Agree
7	My teaching methods effectively address the diverse cultural background of my students.	4.00	Agree
Overall Mean		3.91	Agree

Mean	Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
3.40-4.19	Agree
2.60-3.39	Neutral
1.80-2.59	Disagree
1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Table 3.1
Students' Satisfaction on Quality of Instruction

No.	Students' Satisfaction on Quality of Instruction		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	My music teacher explains musical concepts clearly.	4.82	High Support
2	My music teacher's delivery makes the class engaging.	4.79	High Support
3	The classroom environment is suitable for learning music.	4.51	High Support
4	My music teacher adapts lessons when needed to help us learn.	4.78	High Support
5	My music teacher uses creative methods in teaching.	4.77	High Support
Overall Mean		4.74	High Support

Mean	Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00	High Support
3.40-4.19	Support
2.60-3.39	Moderate Support
1.80-2.59	Fair Support
1.00-1.79	No Support

**Table 3.2
Student Engagement**

No.	Student Engagement		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I feel actively involved in music class activities.	4.60	Strongly Agree
2	Music class helps me express my emotions.	4.63	Strongly Agree
3	I enjoy collaborating with my classmates in music activities.	4.59	Strongly Agree
4	I am motivated to participate in music class.	4.61	Strongly Agree
5	I look forward to my music classes.	4.74	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		4.63	Strongly Agree

Mean	Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
3.40-4.19	Agree
2.60-3.39	Neutral
1.80-2.59	Disagree
1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

**Table 3.3
Students Outcomes**

No.	Student Outcomes		
	Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I have improved my ability to read notes	4.67	Strongly Agree
2	I feel more confident in my musical abilities now than at the start of the year.	4.35	Strongly Agree
3	Music class has helped me understand different cultures.	4.51	Strongly Agree
4	Music class helps me manage stress or feel better emotionally.	4.59	Strongly Agree
5	I feel my creativity has improved through music class.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		4.53	Strongly Agree

Mean	Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
3.40-4.19	Agree
2.60-3.39	Neutral
1.80-2.59	Disagree
1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Table 4
Challenges Encountered by Music Teachers

No.	Challenges Encountered by Music Teachers		
	STATEMENTS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Educators do not have sufficient time for reflecting on their teaching practice.	3.40	Serious
2	Proper access to professional development programs related to reflective teaching is lacking.	3.56	Serious
3	Teachers are resistant to learning new instructional techniques or approaches.	3.17	Moderately Serious
4	Inadequate support or constructive criticism from peers or mentors towards reflective practice.	3.23	Moderately Serious
5	Excessive workload does not allow teachers to reflect meaningfully.	3.44	Moderately Serious
6	There are no clear frameworks or guidelines for teachers to use in reflective practice.	3.28	Serious
7	There is a lack of administrative support for teachers to engage in reflective practices.	3.23	Serious
8	Administrators provide insufficient resources (time, funding, training) to facilitate teacher reflection and the implementation of change.	3.37	Moderately Serious
9	Administrators prioritize compliance with regulations over fostering a culture of continuous improvement and reflection.	3.53	Very Serious
10	Administrators lack adequate training on how to effectively support and guide reflective practice among staff.	3.44	Very Serious
Overall Mean		3.37	Moderately Serious

Mean	Verbal Interpretations
4.20-5.00	Very serious
3.40-4.19	Serious
2.60-3.39	Moderately Serious
1.80-2.59	Slightly Serious
1.00-1.79	Not Serious

DISCUSSION

Level of Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program

Table 1.1 shows the responses for Administrators' Support to Music Major Teachers in the SPA program in terms of Musical Instruments. Statement 4 "My school administration determines the needs of teachers in terms of musical instruments" has the highest mean of 3.86 that is equivalent to a verbal interpretation of "High Support". The statement with the lowest mean is number 5, "My school administration maintains the quality of musical instruments and do repairs if needed." It has a mean of 3.43 that is equivalent to "High Support". This indicates that the administrators are doing their best to

provide the needs of the teachers for instruction particularly musical instrument. This result clearly implies that administrative support, provision of tools, funding, professional growth, and policy coherence, have the key role in facilitating teachers to put into practice creative, adaptable teaching (Rinta & Welch, 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023) role in facilitating teachers to put into practice creative, adaptable teaching (Rinta & Welch, 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023).

To address the concerns of the music teachers is the second area under administrator's support. **Table 1.2** contains the responses in terms of mean and verbal interpretation. Statement 2, "My principal/ coordinator actively listens to my concerns regarding music teaching." has the highest mean of 3.86 with an interpretation of high support. Statement 4, "My principal/coordinator addresses music teachers' concerns on time." has the lowest mean of 3.63 which has the same interpretation of high support. This means that the administrators are giving appropriate attention to the concerns of the teachers. This also implies that when concerns of music teachers arise, their administrators do their best to address them.

This finding was similar to that of Kemal Kayikçi et. Al. (2017) that having leaders who live up to their words, coaching, and skill-based training can all help people become more adept at handling conflict.

Table 1.3 presents the administration support in terms of giving feedback, Statement 2, "The feedback given to me by my administrator are constructive in nature." has the highest mean of 3.86 in rating. This corresponds to a verbal interpretation of "High Support". On the other hand, statement 4, "My administrator's way of giving feedback is very professional and objective." has the lowest mean of 3.63 that corresponds to a verbal interpretation of high support.

This result implies that the respondents were satisfied in the way their administrator assessed their instruction by means of giving feedback on their performance. These comments and suggestions from the administrators help in the enhancement of teachers' performance. This result was in coherence with that of Diz-Otero et al. (2023) that communication is one of the important skills which are vital in the overall development of students, like giving feedback.

Table 1.4 shows the administration support in terms of professional development. Statement 1, "The school administration encourages teachers to participate in seminars and trainings." has the highest mean of 3.81 (High Support), while statement 5, "The school looks for possible help and assistance for teachers enrolled in the graduate studies." has the lowest mean of 3.51 (High Support). This finding reflects the support given by the administrator in terms of teachers' career advancement as far as their teaching is concerned.

This implies that teachers are provided with different opportunities and support for development to enhance their teaching performance. This finding was further supported by that of Brillantes & Fernandez (2011), that regional offices were able to show their

leadership and agility in meeting instructional needs through provision of different professional development activities.

The last area under administrative support is the teaching method. **Table 1.5** has data in terms of mean and verbal interpretation. Statement 2, “My administration provides training and capacity building in handling music subject.” had the highest mean of 3.80 that is equivalent to a verbal interpretation of “High Support.” However, statement 4, “My administration plans projects that support the teaching-learning process in music. “Has the lowest mean of 3.54 that corresponds to a verbal interpretation of “High Support). This means that the administrators are extending support to teachers relative to their venture of applying different methods of instruction.

This result was strengthened by the study of Biasutti (2020) and Abril (2019) that emphasized the pedagogic benefits of improvisational teaching in developing cognitive flexibility, affective expression, social interaction, and musical imagination.

Extent of Teacher Pedagogical Practices of Music Teachers in SPA

Table 2 has the ratings under extent of teacher pedagogical practices of music teachers in SPA, Statement 4, “My teaching methods effectively address the diverse cultural background of my students.” has the highest mean of 4.00 and statement 1, “I frequently use student-chosen music in my lessons.” has the lowest mean with 3.77. All the statements were given a rating that is equivalent to a verbal interpretation of “Agree.” This means that all the mentioned statements are being practiced by the teachers in their classroom instruction. This result implies that music teachers are adopting different teaching practices that are suitable to the needs of the students. This means that the music teachers are practicing all the indicated activities in their classes.

This finding was supported by that of Williams (2019) that music education has shifted from a pedagogical paradigm based on the transmission of traditional praxis to an approach that is more focused on the overall development and personal growth of pupils.

Level of Student Satisfaction for Teachers of Music in the SPA

Table 3.1 presents the responses for students’ perception of instructional quality in terms of mean and verbal interpretation. For students’ perception of instructional quality, Statement 1, “My music teacher explains musical concepts clearly.” Had the highest mean of 4.82 that is equivalent to a verbal interpretation of “Excellent”. The statement with the lowest mean of 4.51 is Statement 3, “The classroom environment is suitable for learning music.” However, all the given statements were rated as “Excellent.” This result means that the students have very positive perception towards the quality of their teachers’ instruction.

This finding was an illustration of the definition of unscripted instruction given by McPherson & Welch, (2021), that unscripted teaching is an adaptive, student-centered

pedagogy that values flexibility, imagination, and responsiveness to students' unique needs.

In terms of student engagement, **Table 3.2** shows the results. Statement 5, "I look forward to my music classes." Had the highest mean of 4.74 while Statement 3, "I enjoy collaborating with my classmates in music activities." Had the lowest mean of 4.59.

On the other hand, all the given statements were rated as "Excellent." This means that students were having their most active participation in the activities related to music subject. This result was in accordance with that of Sun (2022), that learning music positively impacts students' academic performance and socio-emotional well-being, as evidenced by enhanced self-efficacy and self-esteem.

Table 3.3 presents the mean and verbal interpretation for student outcomes. It was Statement 1, "I have improved my ability to read notes." That has the highest mean of 4.67 and Statement 2, "I feel more confident in my musical abilities now than at the start of the year." Has the lowest mean of 4.35, but all the statements were given a mean that corresponds to a verbal interpretation of "Excellent." These findings were further supported by that of Southgate & Roscigno (2021), and Hallam (2019), that music education is a key factor in the formation of students' identities, the encouragement of creativity, enhancement of executive functioning, and the development of emotional resilience. This implies that the students showed improvement in their performance and skills in their music subject.

Challenges Encountered that can be used for reflection and change

Table 4 contains the challenges encountered by teacher in teaching music. Based on the results, Statement 2, "Proper access to professional development programs related to reflective teaching is lacking." has the highest mean of 3.56 that is equal to a verbal interpretation of "Serious." This finding reveals that the teachers are experiencing difficulty in their access to different professional programs that is related to reflective teaching. Statement 3, "Teachers are resistant to learning new instructional techniques or approaches." Has the lowest mean of 3.17 and is equivalent to a verbal interpretation of "Moderately Serious." This means that teachers have minimal difficulty in terms of being resistant to new learning about instructional techniques and approaches as far as music teaching is concern. This finding was a manifestation of Brillantes (2022), that there is lack of specialized training for teachers of music that makes them experienced the difficulties mentioned.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the researcher derived the following conclusions:

1. The music teachers expressed a high level of support from their administrator in terms of musical instruments, addressing concerns, giving feedback, professional development and teaching method.

2. The teachers showed that they are in actual practice of the activities related to their unscripted instruction and teaching delivery.
3. The students categorized their own outcomes as excellent in terms of their perception of instructional quality, engagement and outcomes in music subject.
4. The teachers experienced most difficulty in proper access to professional development programs related to reflective teaching and their compliance in accordance with regulations.
5. An action plan was developed that mainly aims to address the challenges encountered by the teachers relative to the accomplishment of their task and their need for access to a professional development plan.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. It was illustrated in this study that a high level of support from their administrator in terms of musical instruments, addressing concerns, giving feedback, professional development and teaching methods was given to the teachers. The researcher recommends that the same level of support should be extended to the teachers in other areas such as the provision of appropriate music room and other teaching materials needed.
2. The researcher recommends that music teachers should be exposed to capacity training programs that are suited to their specialization and accomplishment of their work as music teachers in the special program for the arts.
3. The researcher recommends always diagnose students' performance to be used as basis and inputs in planning for instructional designs and activities.
4. This study recommends the development of different professional development activities that will address the needs and challenges of the teachers
5. The researcher recommends the adaptation of the developed action plan in this study to address the needs of the teachers in enhancing their professional capabilities as music teachers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In all phases of this research, strong ethical standards were observed. Informed consent was obtained from all participants to guarantee that they are completely informed of the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of their participation, their right to withdraw at any time without penalty, and the precautions taken to protect their confidentiality. To safeguard the identities of individuals and institutions, anonymity was

maintained for all responses, particularly in published findings. Before implementation, relevant institutional review boards (IRB) were consulted to get ethical approval for the study protocol, including all data collection instruments and methods. Following data privacy regulations, all data collected were securely stored in password-protected digital files and secured physical cabinets, accessible only by authorized researchers.

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